

Coexistence of Rheumatoid Arthritis with psoriasis causing Diagnostic dilemma in an Immunocompromised host: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic systemic autoimmune disease that primarily affects synovial joints but it can also involve multiple organ systems, including the cardiovascular system. Coexistence of degenerative joint disease and valvular heart disease can further complicate the clinical symptoms and management. We report a case of a 59-year-old male, a known chronic smoker with a history of hypertension and type 2 diabetes mellitus on treatment for psoriasis with erythroderma, who presented with complaints of right knee pain with multiple joint pain, morning stiffness, and progressive limitation of daily activities. Clinical examination revealed features suggestive of inflammatory polyarthritis predominantly involving the small joints of the hands along with signs of degenerative joint involvement and sparing of distal interphalangeal joints (DIP). Laboratory investigations supported the diagnosis of rheumatoid arthritis, while radiological evaluation showed osteoarthritic changes in weight-bearing joints which may be secondary osteoarthritis. Cardiovascular evaluation was performed due to complaints of exertional dyspnea and palpitations. Two-dimensional echocardiography demonstrated progressive mitral stenosis with associated tricuspid regurgitation. The coexistence of rheumatoid arthritis, osteoarthritis, and valvular heart disease in a patient with multiple cardiovascular risk factors highlights the systemic nature of RA and the importance of detailed evaluation. This case emphasizes the need for early diagnosis of extra-articular manifestations and cardiovascular complications in patients with rheumatoid arthritis, particularly in individuals with comorbid conditions such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and chronic smoking. Multidisciplinary management and regular cardiovascular monitoring are essential to improve outcomes and prevent disease progression.

Keywords: Rheumatoid Arthritis, Psoriasis, Osteoarthritis, Mitral stenosis.

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) is a chronic systemic autoimmune inflammatory disorder characterized by persistent synovial inflammation, progressive joint destruction, and multiple extra-articular manifestations. Beyond articular involvement, RA is associated with significant systemic complications affecting the cardiovascular, pulmonary, and nervous systems. Cardiovascular disease represents one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality among patients with RA due to chronic systemic inflammation and vascular pathology.¹

Cardiac involvement in RA includes pericarditis, myocarditis, conduction abnormalities, and valvular

heart disease. Chronic inflammatory activity can lead to fibrosis, thickening, and structural damage of cardiac valves, occasionally accompanied by rheumatoid nodules within valve leaflets. These pathological changes may ultimately result in valvular dysfunction presenting as regurgitation or stenosis.²

Echocardiographic studies have demonstrated that structural cardiac abnormalities are relatively common in RA patients. In a recent Doppler echocardiographic evaluation, approximately 14% of patients with RA were found to have valvular abnormalities, including mitral and tricuspid valve disease.³

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Recent population-based cohort studies have further shown that RA is associated with an increased risk of developing valvular heart disease, particularly aortic valve stenosis, suggesting that chronic inflammation may contribute to degenerative valvular pathology. ⁴

Psoriasis is a chronic skin disease characterized by itchy, scaly patches that commonly appear on the knees, elbows, trunk, and scalp. This case is not Psoriatic Arthritis, as it is a case of seropositive arthritis and psoriatic changes of skin were not associated with the arthropathy. So, this can be a case of Rheumatoid arthritis(RA)with Psoriasis.

Patients with inflammatory arthropathies may also have additional cardiovascular risk factors including smoking, hypertension, and diabetes mellitus, which further increase the risk of cardiovascular complications. The coexistence of RA and psoriasis with significant valvular involvement such as Mitral Stenosis and Tricuspid Regurgitation is rarely described in the literature and highlights the importance of comprehensive cardiovascular evaluation in such patients.

Case Report:

Mr. Shrikant Das, daily wager by profession, 59 year old male patient, presented with complaints of right knee pain & swelling for last 10-12 days prior to the admission, which aggravated in last 2 days before admission. Pain was sudden onset, gradually progressing, non radiating & associated with swelling, reduced upon taking medication. It is not associated with fever, any other joint pain was noted. No H/o any trauma noted. Patient is a K/c/o hypertension & Type 2 DM.

Patient was getting T/t under dermatology department regarding Psoriatic erythroderma for last 30 days. The history of polyarthritis with morning stiffness involving small joints of hand with axial joint and DIP sparing was present 2 months before psoriatic lesions appeared.

Patient was a ex-smoker with H/o 10 pack/year.

O/E:

Pt was A/C/C

BP: 110/60 mmHg

PR: 86/bpm

spo2: 98% on RA

Resp: B/L VBS+

OVS: S1 S2 audible with mid-diastolic murmur

All necessary investigations were done.

✓ RA ⊕

✓ Anti CCP antibody ⊕

✓ MRI Right knee shows : Medial & Lateral meniscus tear

ACL tear

Grade IV patellar chondromalacia with secondary osteoarthritis(Fig 1)

Hands and wrists X Ray showed ulnar deviation, involvement of carpometacarpal, MCP joints with DIP(distal interphalangeal joint) sparing(Fig 2)

✓ HRCT Thorax: COPD features with emphysematous changes.

✓ ECHO 2D: Progressive MS with Tricuspid Regurgitation

Patient was started on HCQS and methotrexate was continued as patient was already on methotrexate and emollient for psoriatic erythroderma and skin lesions were almost resolved with treatment at the time of presentation.

DISCUSSION

Rheumatoid arthritis is increasingly recognized as a systemic inflammatory disease with substantial cardiovascular involvement. Chronic immune-mediated inflammation contributes to endothelial dysfunction, myocardial remodelling, and structural abnormalities within cardiac valves. Studies have shown that patients with RA have a higher incidence of heart failure and structural cardiac disease

compared with the general population.⁵ Valvular heart disease in RA is believed to result from inflammatory infiltration of valve tissue, fibrosis, and immune-mediated damage. Rheumatoid nodules may occasionally develop within valve leaflets, causing thickening and impaired mobility that can lead to regurgitant or stenotic lesion.⁶

Recent echocardiographic studies have demonstrated a significant prevalence of cardiac abnormalities among RA patients. In a Doppler echocardiographic study evaluating cardiac involvement in RA, valvular abnormalities were identified in approximately 14% of patients, with mitral and tricuspid valve involvement being among the most common findings.⁷ Large population-based cohort studies have also shown that RA is associated with an increased risk of valvular heart disease. A study published in 2023 demonstrated that patients with RA had a significantly higher risk of developing aortic stenosis and were more likely to undergo aortic valve replacement compared with individuals without RA.⁸

Advances in cardiac imaging have improved the detection of subclinical cardiac involvement in inflammatory rheumatic diseases. Techniques such as speckle-tracking echocardiography and advanced Doppler imaging allow early identification of myocardial and valvular dysfunction before the onset of clinical symptoms.⁹ The coexistence of RA and Psoriasis is uncommon but has been reported in overlap syndromes. Both conditions share similar inflammatory mechanisms and are associated with increased cardiovascular risk. Persistent systemic inflammation may accelerate structural cardiac changes, particularly in patients with traditional cardiovascular risk factors such as smoking, hypertension, and diabetes mellitus. The diagnosis was Rheumatoid arthritis in a psoriasis patient and not psoriatic arthritis. The symmetrical joint involvement, RA Factor and Anti CCP positivity, DIP sparing made the diagnosis of Rheumatoid Arthritis with psoriasis possible, though psoriatic arthritis may present with psoriasis followed by arthritis.

In the present case, the patient had multiple cardiovascular risk factors including long-standing smoking, hypertension, and type 2 diabetes mellitus. Echocardiographic evaluation revealed progressive

mitral stenosis with associated tricuspid regurgitation. The combined effect of systemic inflammatory disease and metabolic risk factors likely contributed to the development and progression of valvular heart disease in this patient.

Early recognition of cardiac involvement in inflammatory rheumatic diseases is therefore essential. Current recommendations emphasize the role of echocardiographic evaluation in patients with inflammatory arthritis who present with cardiac symptoms or significant cardiovascular risk factors. Early diagnosis and multidisciplinary management involving rheumatologists and cardiologists may help prevent progression to severe valvular dysfunction and heart failure.

Management Modality Of Rheumatoid Arthritis :¹⁰

1. First-Line Treatment: DMARDs

Disease-Modifying Antirheumatic Drugs (DMARDs) are the first line treatment of RA therapy.

Methotrexate (most commonly used first-line drug), Leflunomide, Sulfasalazine, Hydroxychloroquine

2. Biological DMARDs (for moderate–severe RA)

Used when conventional DMARDs are insufficient.

TNF inhibitors: Etanercept, Infliximab

Others: Rituximab (anti CD 20), Tocilizumab (Anti IL6)

3. Targeted Synthetic DMARDs: Tofacitinib, Baricitinib

4. NSAIDs (Symptom Relief) : Ibuprofen, Naproxen

5. Corticosteroids : Prednisone

6. Non-Pharmacological Treatment : Physical therapy & exercise, Lifestyle changes (weight management, smoking cessation), Joint protection techniques

7. Surgical Options : Synovectomy, Joint replacement (e.g., knee or hip)

8. Treatment of psoriatic erythroderma is with immunosuppressants(cyclosporine,methotrexate),Biological therapies like infliximab,oral retinoids and hydration.

CONCLUSION

This case highlights the uncommon coexistence of Rheumatoid Arthritis and Psoriasis with significant valvular heart disease, including Mitral Stenosis and Tricuspid Regurgitation. Chronic systemic inflammation associated with inflammatory arthropathies may contribute to structural cardiac abnormalities, particularly in patients with additional cardiovascular risk factors such as smoking, hypertension, and diabetes mellitus.

This case emphasizes the importance of early cardiovascular evaluation in patients with inflammatory rheumatic diseases, especially those presenting with cardiopulmonary symptoms. Routine clinical assessment and timely echocardiographic screening can facilitate early detection of valvular involvement and guide appropriate multidisciplinary management. Early recognition of cardiac complications may help prevent disease progression and reduce long-term cardiovascular morbidity in patients with systemic inflammatory disorders.

Conflicts of Interest- None

Source of Funding- Nil.

Fig 1: MRI Right knee showing secondary osteoarthritis

Fig 2: Rheumatoid Arthritis X ray Hands and Wrist joints

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